

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF DEPOSITARY AND REGISTRAR INSTITUTIONS ON THE WORLD MARKETS AND THE SPECIFICS OF LEGISLATIVE REGULATION

Adamova Karine

*PhD, Associate Professor,
Department of Financial Markets and Financial Engineering,*

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ИНСТИТУТОВ УЧЕТНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ НА МИРОВЫХ РЫНКАХ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ

Адамова К.Р.

*к.э.н., доцент Департамента финансовых рынков и финансового инжиниринга
Финансовый Университет при Правительстве Российской Федерации
Москва, Россия*

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e*

Abstract

The process of digitalization of the global economy affects all areas of the global financial market, its trading and post-trading infrastructure, and significantly affects and even forms the main trends in the national financial markets of developed and developing countries. Digitalization is the main driver of the modern development of financial markets and contributes to the expansion of investment tools and changes in approaches and technologies of trading and accounting. At the same time, there is a need to ensure the reliability of transactions and ensure the openness of financial markets, facilitate access to national capital markets, unify rules and regulations for transactions, regulate and supervise the financial sector, standardize requirements for transactions and payment and settlement services for participants in transactions.

Аннотация

Процесс цифровизации мировой экономики затрагивает все сферы мирового финансового рынка, его трейдинговую и пост-трейдинговую инфраструктуры, и значительно влияет и даже формирует основные тенденции на национальных финансовых рынках развитых и развивающихся стран. Цифровизация является основным драйвером современного развития финансовых рынков и способствует расширению инструментов инвестиций, изменению подходов и технологий торговли и учета. При этом возникает необходимость обеспечения надежности транзакций и обеспечения открытости финансовых рынков, облегчения доступа к национальным рынкам капиталов, унификации норм и правил осуществления операций, регулирования и надзора за финансовой сферой, стандартизации требований к транзакциям и платежно-расчетному обслуживанию участников операций.

Keywords: digital assets, tokenization, distributed registries, smart contracts, stocks, blockchain, NASDAQ, European Union

Ключевые слова: цифровые активы, токенизация, распределенные реестры, смарт-контракты, акции, блокчейн, NASDAQ, Европейский союз

Digital technologies are currently actively developing abroad and information about the main ideas is being published. Most often, digital transformation is associated with the tokenization¹ of digital assets and other technologies that simplify the accounting and transfer of information about digital assets. All rights to digital assets are accounted for accordingly in the institutions of the depositary and registrar system.

A radical transformation in the financial world can be achieved through modernization, which will completely change the approach to managing, using and monetizing investments. Tokenization opens up new

opportunities for creating a variety of financial products and allows everyone to invest globally, regardless of their income or portfolio size. In a militarized form, physical assets can be represented digitally and secured by distributed registries. It is also possible to issue traditional assets in a paramilitary form.

Tokenization in blockchain technology is the process of converting something of value into a digital token that can be used in a blockchain application. The token is a share of ownership of the underlying asset and can be created for both tangible assets, including gold, real estate, bonds, debts and works of art, as well

¹ Tokenization is the process of replacing valuables (such as money, stocks, credit card numbers, medical records) with

tokens reflecting these values, which makes trading them easier and safer.

as intangible assets, including ownership rights and product licensing. Moreover, indivisible assets can be divided into token forms.

The importance of tokenization goes far beyond access to investments; it could also facilitate the introduction of new investment models. Currently, most investments use shareholder capital in an effort to optimize profits and share price. For example, when you buy shares of a company, you provide money in exchange for a share, but the way the company is run and largely beyond your direct control. Because an organization uses smart contracts², it can manage both financial investments and facilitate voting rights and/or ownership rights related to investments. There is the possibility of incorporating the stakeholder capitalism model, a popular management theory in the 1950s and 60s that promoted benefits provided to the wider community, not just to shareholders.

Is it possible to invest in a company through the use of tokenization with the condition that the CEO does not receive more than 100 times the average earnings of employees, or otherwise the investment will be automatically refunded? The actual figure of the United States is 274 times higher than the average worker's earnings. Alternatively, you can invest in advanced technologies, for example, in the field of computer vision, and link the investment to the fact that the owner will never sell the intellectual property of a company in the defense industry.

The tokenization method allows you to store and transfer native digital assets in a digital blockchain registry, which guarantees a global standard of authenticity. The use of smart contracts ensures fast and consistent execution of transactions, which reduces the amount of administrative work and intermediaries, which, in turn, reduces costs. At the same time, there are problems that need to be solved if we want to use tokenization to transform the market.

Comprehensive work is needed to regulate tokenization, which should include a global taxonomy and token definition. In order to implement such a system more effectively, a stable legal framework and the development of a regulatory framework for defining roles and procedures in the process of creating value for digital assets are required. In addition, it is important to identify the supervisory framework and persons responsible for monitoring and supervision in this area. The combination of these problems with the chaotic nature of the blockchain creates significant obstacles to the large-scale implementation of tokenization.

There are several barriers to industrial-level decision-making and scaling, which makes tokenization less valuable. The technology has a network effect, i.e. its usefulness reaches its maximum when scaled and distributed, which is not sufficiently stimulated at present. As a result, large market players cannot work synchronously, which leads to market fragmentation and reduced liquidity. Despite the consortia's attempts to

solve this problem, they face implementation difficulties, including IP ownership, limited advantages for large players, and difficulties in providing access to new technology companies in the market and fintech companies.

Security issues are growing in blockchain applications, which are being put in a difficult position due to cybersecurity and attacks. However, the creation, management and protection of tokenization still remain technologies in rough development. Therefore, there is a need for a certain infrastructure that would facilitate asset management and make it possible to connect tokenization with legacy systems during its smooth adaptation.

Tokenization, despite possible difficulties, can provide a number of important development factors, bring accessibility through fragmentation and speed up calculations, creating greater liquidity. It is also possible to use the software in different time zones. Fast calculations and high liquidity allow financial institutions to switch from the current T+2 standard to almost real-time calculations. Assets can be sold, settled and used as collateral on the same day, which significantly speeds up the circulation of money and is used for a wide range of economic benefits.

Smart contracts can significantly facilitate and change traditional financial processes, which will increase efficiency and reduce costs for all participants. In blockchain, assets can move almost instantly without restrictions and problems, which makes them more mobile and accessible to everyone. This is a huge potential for investors and issuers who can benefit from all this.

Despite the many opportunities provided by tokenization, the next step is to work on consistent global regulation and the development of production-level solutions that are needed for wider adoption. Financial institutions should start considering the necessary infrastructure to support tokenization, such as adaptation, management and integration with legacy systems, to be ready for the future financial sector, as investments in tokenization technologies continue to grow and the benefits of new assets become more apparent.

In recent years, distributed ledger technology (DLT) has attracted a lot of attention from the financial industry and regulators. DLT is a blockchain technology that arose in connection with the advent of cryptocurrencies, when users issue and verify them, rather than the central government. Tokenization is one of the main DLT-related technologies in which multiple users collaborate to reach consensus on the correct state of data.

Since the moment virtual currencies were born, financial giants have begun to explore the possibility of using DLT in securities trading and performing post-trading operations such as clearing and settlements. The goal is to create safer and more efficient markets, because this issue is currently one of the most pressing. For an in-depth understanding of how trading platforms

² A smart contract is a computer program that executes agreements concluded between two or more parties, as a result of which certain actions occur when certain conditions are met.

function and how the post-trading market infrastructure is built, it is necessary to study this issue more deeply.

In recent years, financial institutions have experimented with several proofs of concept in certain niches of the trading and post-trading environment. For example, the Australian Stock Exchange and Digital Assets are creating a DLT system for clearing and settlement of shares, which is scheduled to launch in 2023. NASDAQ and Skandinaviska Enskilda Banken AB then created a mutual fund trading platform that uses blockchain technology. Since 2019, the French central securities depository ID2S has started using blockchain technology to issue French commercial securities. In addition, the Canadian Securities Exchange is developing a platform using DLT for clearing and settlement of securities. This platform would allow firms to issue shares and fixed income securities through the placement of security tokens. In 2021, Deutsche Börse, in collaboration with Deutsche Bundesbank and the German Financial Agency, developed and tested a settlement interface for electronic securities that allows payments with central bank money. During testing, the German Financial Agency issued ten-year federal bonds (Bund) in the DLT system, where transactions in the primary and secondary markets were also carried out using DLT.[1]

An important goal of the European Commission is to ensure consumers' access to innovative financial products, taking into account both their protection and financial stability. This forms part of the digital action plan, which has four priority areas:

- a) unification of the Single Digital Market,
- b) adaptation of the legal framework legislation of the European Union, taking into account digital innovations,
- c) promotion of data-based financing,
- d) mitigation of risks associated with digital transformation, such as increasing the sustainability of the financial system in the digital environment.

Certain goals have been set to regulate the DLT pilot mode. First of all, the European Commission thought about legal certainty and compliance of the regulatory framework with the intended use of technology. Stimulating innovation is the second goal, and this can only be done by removing legal obstacles to the use of DLT. However, the use of this technology is still limited due to the lack of consideration of legislation, which also acts as a barrier. Previously existing regulations have tried to be technologically neutral, but legal interpretations can be a big obstacle to the development of this innovative technology. It is necessary to adopt new regulations that will take into account the specifics of DLT.

Article 3 of the CSDR [2], for example, may be considered an obstacle, since it requires transferable securities that are traded on the trading floor to be recorded in the form of an entry in CSD or on before the expected settlement date. Thus, a DLT system without the issuer's central depository providing a notarial function may be unacceptable from the issuer's point of view. In addition, Article 38 of the CSDR requires that the Central Securities Depository and its participants in all storage chains separate their clients' securities in

their accounts from those of any other client and, if applicable, from their clients. However, a security account with which a debit or credit operation is possible may not exist in the DLT environment. The European Commission is currently of the opinion that the pilot regime is useful, allowing for the release of some existing market infrastructure requirements for trading and settlement of transferable securities. In this way, these infrastructures can experiment with the technology and assess when and how its full potential will be realized. It will also provide valuable knowledge to legislators to assess whether more extensive changes should be made to existing financial legislation.

The DLT pilot mode focuses on requirements for multilateral trading mechanisms (MTFs) and securities settlement systems (DLT SSS). DLT MTFs are defined as multilateral trading platforms operated by an investment firm or market operator that only allow trading in transferable DLT securities and that can be authorized on the basis of transparent, non-discretionary, uniform rules and procedures to:

- a) ensure initial accounting of transferable DLT securities,
- b) settle transactions in transferable DLT securities against payment,
- c) provide custody services in relation to DLT transferable securities or, where applicable, related payments and collateral provided using DLT MTF.

The securities settlement system, managed by the central securities depository and called DLTS, is designed to settle transactions with securities that will be transferred to DLT. Payment for transactions with securities is carried out by contrasting payments. According to CSDR, the completion of the transaction with the made party occurs when transferring cash, securities or combinations thereof.

The proposal defines «market infrastructures» in a broad sense, as it considers multilateral trading mechanisms (MTFs) as market infrastructures. In contrast, the Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructure (CPMI) and the International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO), which published the Principles of Financial Market Infrastructure [3] on April 16, 2012, consider only payment systems, central securities depositories, central counterparties, securities settlement systems and trading vaults as market infrastructure, but not MTFs. The CSDR then established that central banks can be authorized if they offer at least a securities settlement service, making CSD and SSS rather equivalent. While the financial industry recognizes the role that DLT can play in clearing and settlement activities, it was initially thought that trading platforms or other trading means were less likely to be affected by the technology.

The argument was that trading platforms or an electronic copy available to other trading tools still need to find counterparties, which will not change when using DLT. Rather, the European Commission is of the opinion that DLT can provide settlements in almost real time, thereby making trading and settlements almost instantaneous. Thus, DLT MTFs will be allowed to also provide settlement services, a service that was originally reserved for CSD. Consequently, in the

pilot mode, the requirement that trade and settlements should be carried out by two different institutions is thus no longer imposed. Paradoxically, DLT SSSS are only allowed to settle DLT transferable securities against payment, which means they cannot offer trading services. This can cause problems with equal playing conditions, as DLT MTFs can offer settlement services, while DLT SSS cannot offer trading services. Thus, DLT MTF will be allowed to perform basic notarial and settlement services that are otherwise performed by central depositories, while they only need to comply with a few equivalent Central Depository rules. By performing the same activity, DLT MTF could thus provide CSD services subject to lower regulatory standards than DLT SSS.

With regard to MTF DLT, the proposal provides that they are subject to all the requirements applicable to MTF in accordance with MiFID II and MiFIR [4], except in cases where its operator requests exceptions from its competent authority, which can provide them. Before a DLT market infrastructure operator wants to become active, they must go through the same authorization procedure as a traditional MTF or CSD, but in this way they can specify the exceptions they seek. However, the competent authority may require the operator to comply with additional conditions to ensure investor protection, market integrity and/or financial stability.[5]

The complexity of implementing digital technologies is recognized by many analysts and managers of key banks. Robin Vince, President and Chief Executive Officer of BNY Mellon, commented on this issue: «A comprehensive regulatory framework is needed, but most of its foundations already exist and can be expanded by regulating traditional assets».[6]

To fully realize the potential of the digital asset ecosystem of the future, public and private leaders must work together to create a smart regulatory framework that combines traditional and digital asset systems. Cryptocurrencies may dictate terms in the headlines, but in fact they are only a small part of the world of digital assets. The basis of such a base should be based on two principles. First, regulation should allow the financial industry to use innovations and new technologies wisely. This is a recognition that the old approaches are already becoming irrelevant and it is necessary to bring to life a new approach that will help the industry not to remain in the past.

A fairly long period has already been passed, where many generations of effective financial principles have been observed. With respect to traditional assets, such as cash, stocks and bonds, its presentation in a digital registry can be considered a breakthrough, especially since the original computer registries and real-time payments were paper before them. This development can improve the accuracy of accounting, make it easier to process certain types of assets, such as, for example, real estate and loans, as well as reduce labor intensity and improve the efficiency of calculations.

The new market infrastructure that benefits the financial system can be maintained using distributed ledger technology, which is the basis for crypto assets. There are several examples of taking advantage of this

new technology, such as tokenized bonds and central bank digital currencies, which are being studied by major jurisdictions.

In the fall of 2022, the Federal Reserve Bank of New York and the Monetary Authority of Singapore announced a joint effort to explore how the central bank's wholesale digital currencies can improve the efficiency of cross-border wholesale payments using multiple currencies. [7] Therefore, research and innovation related to digital ledger technology should be encouraged rather than penalized in future regulatory frameworks.

Regardless of the type of organization, asset class, or new technologies, maintaining the basic principles of customer protection, orderly markets, and clear regulatory guidance is the second principle. The financial system as a whole can be undermined if digital assets do not comply with these principles. We should keep in mind that while the characters and products in the financial market may change, the scenario of confusion remains familiar due to the effects of mixed customer assets, poor transparency of information and lack of internal controls.

Despite the active development of technologies, it is necessary to use existing and relevant concepts for all market participants and assets, regardless of their technological state. Among such concepts, it is important to pay attention to adequate management, delineation of customer assets, accurate accounting, compliance with security and technology standards, capital and liquidity, certain limits for credit risks, ensuring protection against money laundering, effective risk management and compliance with regulatory restrictions.

Without rules and a regulatory perimeter, banking institutions will not be able to function and provide their services. Today, thanks to this perimeter, they not only fulfill their obligations, but also receive privileges. An important component of this perimeter is trust, the most valuable currency in the global financial system.

The trust of investors and the public sector is a key factor that determines the success of the financial system as a whole. That is why it is so important to know that there are clear rules in the game. Without trust, our financial system will not be able to provide anything useful and honest.

In addition, it is necessary to understand that the lack of confidence in the financial system can lead to the suppression of the use of new technologies that can help the development of the industry. Thus, the creation and maintenance of rules and regulatory perimeters is a necessity that allows our financial system to exist and develop in a world of constant changes and challenges.

Distributed ledger technology (DLT) is increasingly of interest to institutional investors, and this opens up new prospects in the financial sector. However, the digital asset space is at risk from disruptive innovations to disruptive behavior in general. This may result in limited access to the technology for all interested parties.

To prevent this, a comprehensive regulatory framework is needed, which must be adapted to meet the requirements of the DLT. Many of the principles and rules applied to traditional assets can be extended

to digital assets as well.

It is important to understand that these regulations already exist, and expanding their scope to digital assets will ensure consumer protection, prevent market manipulation and increase transparency in the turnover of digital assets. It is precisely such measures, combined with bold innovations and respect for the rights of all participants, that can make DLT the next financial frontier.

In the search for a way to improve the financial system, it becomes clear that it is necessary to use innovations in the field of digital assets. However, without establishing rules and sound regulatory principles, the risks to customers and the system as a whole may be too high.

In order to achieve a balance between innovation and security, special attention must be paid to protecting trust in the financial system. It is the most valuable asset.

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